

Synthesis and Determination of Dissociation Constants of Two New Acid-Base Indicators

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Acid-base indicators are either weak acids or weak bases. The simplest method to determine the equivalence point in acid-base titrations involves the use of an indicator which changes colour as the pH of the solution changes during the titration. A wide variety of acid-base indicators covering various pH ranges (1.2–12.0) are currently in use. Recently various indicators such as phthalein, sulphonaphthalein¹ and 2-cyano-3,3'-bis(*p*-nitroaniline)acrylonitrile² in highly alkaline solution were characterised based on specific colour discrimination values. Bhuchar and coworkers³ reported the use of *o*-cresol sulphaphthalein, thymol blue and cresol red as indicators in acid-base titrations. We report here the synthesis, characterisation and determination of dissociation constants of two new acid-base indicators, viz. *N,N'*-azobis(4-hydroxy-naphthylidene)-4,4'-sulphedianiline (1) and *N,N'*-azobis(4-hydroxybenzylidene)-4,4'-sulphedianiline (2).

The pK_a values of the indicators were determined using colorimetric measurement⁴. A series of buffers (various mixtures of 0.2 *M* boric acid and 0.2 *M* sodium hydroxide) with pH values in the pK_a range ± 2 were prepared. A fixed volume (5 ml) of the indicator solution (0.001% in absolute alcohol) was added to a fixed volume (25 ml) of each of the buffer solutions and the absorbance of the mixture was measured (at the wavelength equal to λ_{max}). From the measured absorbances A_{max} and A_{min} at pH values of $pK_a + 2$ and $pK_a - 2$ respectively, the absorbance at half-dissociation point was calculated as $A_{hd} = (A_{max} - A_{min})/2$. From a plot of the pH values of the buffer solution against absorbances, the pH value corresponding to an absorbance of A_{hd} was noted and this was taken as the pK_a value of the indicators (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Determination of pK_a for indicator 1.

Fig. 2. Determination of pK_a for indicator 2.

Results and Discussion

The pK_a values of the two indicators (1 and 2) were found to be 7.05 and 7.00 respectively. The analytical utility of these indicators in the titrations of strong or weak acids against strong base was checked by comparing the end-points obtained with that obtained using phenolphthalein indicator. In all the five cases studied, viz. HCl vs NaOH, H_2SO_4 vs NaOH, CH_3COOH vs NaOH, $ClCH_2COOH$ vs NaOH and $HCOOH$ vs NaOH the end-points matched perfectly.

Uv-visible spectra of compounds 1 and 2 showed absorption maxima at 592 and 377 nm respectively. This is due to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of the azo groups⁵. The higher shift in the case of compound 1 may be due to the extended conjugation. The ir spectra of these compounds showed the absence of characteristic frequency of the primary amino group of their precursor and the presence of a strong band at 3500 cm^{-1} due to OH group. The 1H nmr spectra of these compounds showed resonances for the OH protons at δ 1.5 and for the aromatic protons at δ 7.2.

Experimental

The procedure followed is essentially the same as in our previous report⁶. To an ice-cold solution of 4,4'-diaminodiphenylsulphone (Aldrich; 0.03 mol in 100 ml H_2O) and concentrated HCl (10 ml), was added a solution of $NaNO_2$ (0.1 mol in 50 ml H_2O) maintaining the temperature around 0° . This was then followed by the dropwise addition of a solution of 1-naphthol or phenol (0.1 mol in 50 ml 10% NaOH) as the case may be, taking